

Grant Number: 5D43TW001508-10

Principal Investigator(s):
RONALD H GRAY, MD

Project Title: International Training/Research in Population and Health, Uganda

Alexandra McKeown
ASSOC DEAN FOR RESEARCH ADMIN
JOHNS HOPKINS UNIVERSITY
BLOOMBERG, SCHOOL OF PUBLIC HLTH
615 NORTH WOLFE STREET
BALTIMORE, MD 21205

Award e-mailed to: NIH@RESOURCE.CA.JHU.EDU

Budget Period: 04/01/2010 – 03/31/2011

Project Period: 09/29/2000 – 03/31/2011

Dear Business Official:

The National Institutes of Health hereby awards a grant in the amount of \$175,744 (see "Award Calculation" in Section I and "Terms and Conditions" in Section III) to JOHNS HOPKINS UNIVERSITY in support of the above referenced project. This award is pursuant to the authority of 42 USC 241 and is subject to the requirements of this statute and regulation and of other referenced, incorporated or attached terms and conditions.

Acceptance of this award including the "Terms and Conditions" is acknowledged by the grantee when funds are drawn down or otherwise obtained from the grant payment system.

Each publication, press release or other document that cites results from NIH grant-supported research must include an acknowledgment of NIH grant support and disclaimer such as "The project described was supported by Award Number D43TW001508 from the Fogarty International Center. The content is solely the responsibility of the authors and does not necessarily represent the official views of the Fogarty International Center or the National Institutes of Health."

Award recipients are required to comply with the NIH Public Access Policy. This includes submission to PubMed Central (PMC), upon acceptance for publication, an electronic version of a final peer-reviewed, manuscript resulting from research supported in whole or in part, with direct costs from National Institutes of Health. The author's final peer-reviewed manuscript is defined as the final version accepted for journal publication, and includes all modifications on the publishing peer review process. For additional information, please visit <http://publicaccess.nih.gov/>.

Award recipients must promote objectivity in research by establishing standards to ensure that the design, conduct and reporting of research funded under NIH-funded awards are not biased by a conflicting financial interest of an Investigator. Investigator is defined as the Principal Investigator and any other person who is responsible for the design, conduct, or reporting of NIH-funded research or proposed research, including the Investigator's spouse and dependent children. Awardees must have a written administrative process to identify and manage financial conflict of interest and must inform Investigators of the conflict of interest policy and of the Investigators' responsibilities. Prior to expenditure of these awarded funds, the Awardee must report to the NIH Awarding Component the existence of a conflicting interest and within 60 days of any new conflicting interests identified after the initial report. Awardees must comply with these and all other aspects of 42 CFR Part 50, Subpart F. These requirements also apply to subgrantees, contractors, or collaborators engaged by the Awardee under this award. The NIH website <http://grants.nih.gov/grants/policy/coi/index.htm> provides additional information.

If you have any questions about this award, please contact the individual(s) referenced in Section IV.

Sincerely yours,

BRUCE R BUTRUM
Grants Management Officer
FOGARTY INTERNATIONAL CENTER

Additional information follows

SECTION I – AWARD DATA – 5D43TW001508-10**Award Calculation (U.S. Dollars)**

Salaries and Wages	\$7,918
Fringe Benefits	\$2,574
Personnel Costs (Subtotal)	\$10,492
Training Expenses	\$30,269
Stipends	\$60,667
Trainee Tuition/Fees	\$33,463
Trainee Travel	\$30,314

Federal Direct Costs	\$165,205
Federal F&A Costs	\$10,539
Approved Budget	\$175,744
Federal Share	\$175,744
TOTAL FEDERAL AWARD AMOUNT	\$175,744

AMOUNT OF THIS ACTION (FEDERAL SHARE)	\$175,744
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SUMMARY TOTALS FOR ALL YEARS		
YR	THIS AWARD	CUMULATIVE TOTALS
10	\$175,744	\$175,744

Fiscal Information:

CFDA Number:	93.989
EIN:	1520595110A5
Document Number:	DTW001508B
Fiscal Year:	2010

	IC	CAN	2010
HD		8471499	\$48,510
TW		8476374	\$127,234

NIH Administrative Data:**PCC: POP / OC: 412R / Processed:**eRA Commons
User Name

03/23/2010

SECTION II – PAYMENT/HOTLINE INFORMATION – 5D43TW001508-10

For payment and HHS Office of Inspector General Hotline information, see the NIH Home Page at <http://grants.nih.gov/grants/policy/awardconditions.htm>.

SECTION III – TERMS AND CONDITIONS – 5D43TW001508-10

This award is based on the application submitted to, and as approved by, NIH on the above-titled project and is subject to the terms and conditions incorporated either directly or by reference in the following:

- The grant program legislation and program regulation cited in this Notice of Award.
- Conditions on activities and expenditure of funds in other statutory requirements, such as those included in appropriations acts.
- 45 CFR Part 74 or 45 CFR Part 92 as applicable.
- The NIH Grants Policy Statement, including addenda in effect as of the beginning date of the budget period.
- This award notice, INCLUDING THE TERMS AND CONDITIONS CITED BELOW.

(See NIH Home Page at <http://grants.nih.gov/grants/policy/awardconditions.htm> for certain references cited above.)

This institution is a signatory to the Federal Demonstration Partnership (FDP) Phase V Agreement which requires active institutional participation in new or ongoing FDP demonstrations and pilots.

An unobligated balance may be carried over into the next budget period without Grants Management Officer prior approval.

This grant is excluded from Streamlined Noncompeting Award Procedures (SNAP). In accordance with P.L. 110-161, compliance with the NIH Public Access Policy is now mandatory. For more information, see NOT-OD-08-033 and the Public Access website: <http://publicaccess.nih.gov/>.

This award represents the final year of the competitive segment for this grant. Therefore, see the NIH Grants Policy Statement (12/1/2003 version) for closeout requirements at: http://grants.nih.gov/grants/policy/nihgps_2003/NIHGPS_Part8.htm#_Toc54600151.

A final Financial Status Report (FSR) (SF 269) must be submitted through the eRA Commons (Commons) within 90 days of the expiration date; see NIH Guide Notice [NOT-OD-07-078](#) for additional information on this electronic submission requirement. The final FSR must indicate the exact balance of unobligated funds and may not reflect any unliquidated obligations. There must be no discrepancies between the final FSR and the Payment Management System's (PMS) Federal Cash Transaction Report (SF-272).

Furthermore, unless an application for competitive renewal is submitted, additional grant closeout documents consisting of a Final Invention Statement and Certification form (HHS 568), (not applicable to training, construction, conference or cancer education grants) and a final progress report must also be submitted within 90 days of the expiration date.

NIH also strongly encourages electronic submission of the final progress report and the final invention statement through the Closeout feature in the Commons. If the final progress report and final invention statement are not submitted electronically, copies of the HHS 568 form may be downloaded at: <http://grants.nih.gov/grants/forms.htm>.

Submissions of the final progress report and HHS 568 may be e-mailed as PDF attachments to the NIH Central Closeout Center at: deascentralized@od.nih.gov

Paper submissions of the final progress report and the HHS 568 may be faxed to the NIH Central Closeout Center at 301-480-2304 or mailed to the NIH Central Closeout Center at the following address:

NIH/OD/OER/DEAS
Central Closeout Center
6705 Rockledge Drive, Room 2207
Bethesda, MD 20892-7987 (for regular or U.S. Postal Service Express mail)
Bethesda, MD 20817 (for other courier/express mail delivery only)

The final progress report should include, at a minimum, a summary of progress toward the achievement of the originally stated aims, a list of significant results (positive and/or negative), a list of publications and the grant number. If human subjects were included in the research, the final progress report should also address the following:

- Report on the inclusion of gender and minority study subjects (using the gender and minority Inclusion Enrollment Form as provided in the PHS 2590 and available at <http://grants.nih.gov/grants/forms.htm>).
- Where appropriate, indicate whether children were involved in the study or how the study was relevant for conditions affecting children (see "Public Policy Requirements and

Objectives-Requirements for Inclusiveness in Research Design-Inclusion of Children as Subjects in Clinical Research” in the PHS 398 at URL http://grants.nih.gov/grants/policy/nihgps_2003/NIHGPS_Part5.htm#_Toc54600090)

- Describe any data, research materials (such as cell lines, DNA probes, animal models), protocols, software, or other information resulting from the research that is available to be shared with other investigators and how it may be accessed.

Note, if this is the final year of a competitive segment due to the transfer of the grant to another institution, then not all the requirements stated above are applicable. Specifically a Final Progress Report is not required. However, a final FSR is required and should be submitted electronically as noted above. In addition, if not already submitted, the Final Invention Statement is required and should be sent directly to the assigned Grants Management Specialist.

This award is funded by the following list of institutes. Any papers published under the auspices of this award must cite the funding support of all institutes.

Eunice Kennedy Shriver National Institute Of Child Health & Human Development (NICHD) Fogarty International Center (FIC)

Treatment of Program Income:

Additional Costs

SECTION IV – TW Special Terms and Conditions – 5D43TW001508-10

FUNDING LEVEL

This non-competing award is issued in accord with the FIC FY10 Funding Strategy: http://www.fic.nih.gov/funding/fy_strategy/2010funding.htm and is consistent with the NIH Fiscal Policy Notice NOT-OD-10-039: <http://grants.nih.gov/grants/guide/notice-files/NOT-OD-10-039.html>.

CURRENT AND FUTURE YEAR LEVELS

In accordance with the October 27, 1995, NIH Guide announcement and NIH implementation, future-year recommended levels are shown as total costs (the sum of direct plus facilities and administrative costs).

PUBLICATIONS

All publications resulting from the research or research training supported by this award must acknowledge FIC and any co-funders (if applicable). This publication requirement applies not only to the primary grantee, but also to any subcontractors and /or trainees involved with the project.

CONSORTIUM/CONTRACTUAL COSTS

This award includes funds for consortium activities. Consortia are to be established and administered in accordance with the NIH Grants Policy Statement.

TUITION, FEES AND HEALTH INSURANCE RESTRICTION

Funds for tuition, academic fees and self-only or family medical insurance for trainees exceeds 20 percent of total direct costs per the submitted progress report. The grantee is restricted from exceeding the approved tuition, academic fees and self-only or family medical insurance costs as requested on the submitted progress report. Exceptions to this restriction must be approved in writing by the FIC awarding office.

HUMAN SUBJECTS IRB APPROVAL

The Fogarty International Center has received documentation of the applicant organization's valid IRB approval for this project. The applicant organization is responsible for ensuring that any consortium/subcontract organization, involved in human subject research activities with this grant, have an appropriate IRB approval.

REQUIRED EDUCATION IN THE PROTECTION OF HUMAN RESEARCH PARTICIPANTS

Investigators must ensure that the description of the education completed in the protection of human subjects for each individual, identified as "key personnel", in the proposed research has been documented and provided to the FIC awarding office. Key personnel include all individuals responsible for the design and conduct of the study. The Notice for this policy can be found at: <http://grants.nih.gov/grants/guide/notice-files/NOT-OD-00-039.html>.

GENDER AND MINORITY INCLUSION

If this grant proposes the use of human subjects, future non-competing applications require that you indicate the number, ethnicity, and gender of human subjects that are part of this study. If this information is not included in future non-competing grant applications, the funding for the application may be delayed.

RESEARCH MISCONDUCT

The regulations governing research misconduct require the grantee to submit an annual report (Form 6349) to the Office of Research Integrity (ORI) detailing aggregate information on allegations, inquiries, and investigations handled by the grantee in the previous year. ORI automatically sends this form to NIH grantees at the end of the calendar year.

Any questions regarding misconduct issues may be addressed to the office below:

Robin Parker,
Assurance Program Manager
Office of Research Integrity
Division of Education and Integrity
1101 Wootton Parkway, Suite 750
Rockville, MD 20852
Phone # 240-453-8400
Fax # 301-443-5351
Robin.parker@hhs.gov
<http://ori.dhhs.gov/assurance/fis.shtml>

FOREIGN TRAVEL

U.S. Flag carriers must be used for departure from or entry into the U.S. and for any other portion of the trip where available.

FINANCIAL STATUS REPORTS (Standard Form 269)

In accordance with the NIH Grants Policy Statement, non-SNAP grantees must submit an annual Financial Status Report (FSR) within 90 days of the end date of each budget period. The FSR must be submitted in English, in terms of U.S. dollars and use the current rate in existence at the time it is prepared. The Financial Status Report must be submitted via the eRA Commons: <https://commons.era.nih.gov/commons/>. Questions regarding the FSR may also be addressed here:

Contact: Shannon Hershman
Government Accounting Branch
Office of Financial Management
National Institutes of Health
2115 East Jefferson St., MSC 8500
Room 4B432
Bethesda, MD 20892-8500
<http://ofm.od.nih.gov/fsr.asp>

For up-to-date information, you may access the NIH Home Page at <http://www.nih.gov/> and the FIC Home Page at <http://www.fic.nih.gov/>.

STAFF CONTACTS

The Grants Management Specialist is responsible for the negotiation, award and administration of this project and for interpretation of Grants Administration policies and provisions. The Program

Official is responsible for the scientific, programmatic and technical aspects of this project. These individuals work together in overall project administration. Prior approval requests (signed by an Authorized Organizational Representative) should be submitted in writing to the Grants Management Specialist. Requests may be made via e-mail.

Grants Management Specialist: Rhea Hubbard
Email: hubbardrhea@mail.nih.gov **Phone:** 301-496-5710 **Fax:** 301-594-1211

Program Official: Xingzhu Liu
Email: liuxing@mail.nih.gov **Phone:** 301-496-1653 **Fax:** 301-402-0779

SPREADSHEET SUMMARY
GRANT NUMBER: 5D43TW001508-10

INSTITUTION: JOHNS HOPKINS UNIVERSITY

<i>Budget</i>	<i>Year 10</i>
Salaries and Wages	\$7,918
Fringe Benefits	\$2,574
Personnel Costs (Subtotal)	\$10,492
Training Expenses	\$30,269
Stipends	\$60,667
Trainee Tuition/Fees	\$33,463
Trainee Travel	\$30,314
TOTAL FEDERAL DC	\$165,205
TOTAL FEDERAL F&A	\$10,539
TOTAL COST	\$175,744

<i>Facilities and Administrative Costs</i>	<i>Year 10</i>
F&A Cost Rate 1	8%
F&A Cost Base 1	\$131,742
F&A Costs 1	\$10,539

Progress Report Scanning Cover Sheet

5D43TW001508-10

PI Name: **GRAY, RONALD**
Org: **JOHNS HOPKINS UNIVERSITY**
Start Date: **04/01/2010**
Snap: **N) (NEEDS TO BE BOOKMARKED)**
Appl ID: **7799862**
Rec'd Date: **02/01/2010**

Department of Health and Human Services
Public Health Services

Review Group	Type	Activity	Grant Number
	5	D43	TW 001503-10
Total Project Period			
From: 09/29/2006		Through: 03/31/2011	
Requested Budget Period			
From: 04/01/2010		Through: 03/31/2011	

Grant Progress Report

1. TITLE OF PROJECT International Training/Research In Population and Health, Uganda			
2a. PROGRAM DIRECTOR / PRINCIPAL INVESTIGATOR (Name and address, street, city, state, zip code) Ronald H. Gray 615 N. Wolfe Street / E4132A Baltimore, MD 21205		2b. E-MAIL ADDRESS rgray@jhsph.edu	
		2c. DEPARTMENT, SERVICE, LABORATORY, OR EQUIVALENT Population, Family and Reproductive Health	
		2d. MAJOR SUBDIVISION Bloomberg School of Public Health	
		2e. Tel: 410-955-7818 Fax: 410-614-7386	
3a. APPLICANT ORGANIZATION (Name and address, street, city, state, zip code) Johns Hopkins University 615 N. Wolfe Street Baltimore, MD 21205		3b. Tel: 410-614-2636 Fax: 410-955-0258	
		3c. DUNS: 00-191-0777	
		4. ENTITY IDENTIFICATION NUMBER 1520595110-A5	
		FEB 11 2010	
6. HUMAN SUBJECTS <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Yes		5. NAME, TITLE AND ADDRESS OF ADMINISTRATIVE OFFICIAL	
6a. Research Exempt <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Yes		Alexandra A. McKeown, MBA, JD, Associate Dean for Research Administration 615 N. Wolfe St., Suite W1600, Baltimore, MD 21205	
If Exempt ("Yes" in 6a): Exemption No.		If Not Exempt ("No" in 6a): IRB approval date	
6b. Federal Wide Assurance No.		Tel: 410-614-2636 Fax: 410-955-0258	
6c. NIH-Defined Phase III Clinical Trial <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Yes		E-MAIL: amckeown@jhsph.edu	
7. VERTEBRATE ANIMALS <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Yes		10. PROJECT/PERFORMANCE SITE(S)	
7a. If "Yes," IACUC approval Date		Organizational Name: Johns Hopkins University	
7b. Animal Welfare Assurance No.		DUNS: 00-191-0777	
8. COSTS REQUESTED FOR NEXT BUDGET PERIOD		Street 1: 615 N. Wolfe Street	
8a. DIRECT \$165,205		Street 2:	
8b. TOTAL \$175,744		City: Baltimore	
9. INVENTIONS AND PATENTS <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Yes		County: Baltimore City	
If "Yes," <input type="checkbox"/> Previously Reported <input type="checkbox"/> Not Previously Reported		State: MD	
		Province:	
		Country: USA	
		Zip/Postal Code: 21205	
		Congressional Districts: 7th	
11. NAME AND TITLE OF OFFICIAL SIGNING FOR APPLICANT ORGANIZATION (Item 13) Alexandra A. McKeown, MBA, JD			
TEL: 410-614-2636		FAX: 410-955-0258	E-MAIL: amckeown@jhsph.edu
12. Corrections to Page 1 Face Page			
13. APPLICANT ORGANIZATION CERTIFICATION AND ACCEPTANCE: I certify that the statements herein are true, complete and accurate to the best of my knowledge, and accept the obligation to comply with Public Health Services terms and conditions if a grant is awarded as a result of this application. I am aware that any false, fictitious, or fraudulent statements or claims may subject me to criminal, civil, or administrative penalties.		SIGNATURE OF OFFICIAL NAMED IN 11. (In ink)	DATE
			1/29/10

Program Director/Principal Investigator (Last, First, Middle): Gray, Ronald H.

DETAILED BUDGET FOR NEXT BUDGET PERIOD – DIRECT COSTS ONLY	FROM 04/01/2010	THROUGH 03/31/2011	GRANT NUMBER 5D43TW001508
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List PERSONNEL (*Applicant organization only*)
 Use Cal, Acad, or Summer to Enter Months Devoted to Project
 Enter Dollar Amounts Requested (*omit cents*) for Salary Requested and Fringe Benefits

NAME	ROLE ON PROJECT	Cal.	Acad.	Summer	SALARY REQUESTED	FRINGE BENEFITS	TOTALS
		Mnths	Mnths	Mnths			
Gray, Ronald	PD/PI	EFFORT			1,995	649	2,644
Myers, Taryn	Coordinator				5,923	1,925	7,848
SUBTOTALS →					7,918	2,574	10,492

CONSULTANT COSTS
N/A

EQUIPMENT (*Itemize*)
N/A

SUPPLIES (*Itemize by category*)
N/A

TRAVEL

INPATIENT CARE COSTS

OUTPATIENT CARE COSTS

ALTERATIONS AND RENOVATIONS (*Itemize by category*)
N/A

OTHER EXPENSES (*Itemize by category*)
see next page

SUBTOTAL DIRECT COSTS FOR NEXT BUDGET PERIOD \$ 10,492

CONSORTIUM/CONTRACTUAL COSTS DIRECT COSTS

CONSORTIUM/CONTRACTUAL COSTS FACILITIES AND ADMINISTRATIVE COSTS

TOTAL DIRECT COSTS FOR NEXT BUDGET PERIOD (*Item 8a, Face Page*) \$

Program Director/Principal Investigator (Last, first, middle): Gray, Ronald H.

NEXT BUDGET PERIOD <i>(Follow instructions carefully)</i>	FROM 04/01/2010	THROUGH 03/31/2011	GRANT NUMBER 5D43TW001508
ITEMIZE DIRECT COSTS REQUESTED FOR NEXT BUDGET PERIOD			DOLLAR AMOUNT REQUESTED (omit cents)
PREDOCTORAL STIPENDS <i>(List trainee names)</i>			
Robert Ssekubugu <input type="text" value="Personal Info"/> (4 mo. after returning to JHSPH); New Admit, TBN - \$26,000 (stipend based on JHU Fogarty AITRP levels for consistency b/n programs); F. Nalugoda; G. Kigozi, G. Nakigozi, T. Lutalo <input type="text" value="Personal Info"/> R. Kairania, J. Sekasanvu - <input type="text" value="Personal Info"/> <div style="text-align: right;">No. Requested: 8 \$ 60,667</div>			
POSTDOCTORAL STIPENDS <i>(Itemize) (List trainee names and levels)</i>			
<div style="text-align: right;">No. Requested: \$</div>			
OTHER STIPENDS <i>(Specify)</i>			
<div style="text-align: right;">\$</div>			
TOTAL STIPENDS →			\$ 60,667
TUITION and FEES <i>(including Health Insurance when applicable – see new Instructions) (Itemize)</i>			
<i>(List each category separately)</i>			
Partial tuition for TBN new admit - \$7,705 (remainder cost-shared with JHU AITRP); Sandwich PhD tuition at JHU - \$8,000; Sandwich PhD tuition in country - \$6,000; In- country masters tuition - \$6,000 plus fees \$400; in-country bachelors tuition - \$4,758 plus fees \$600. <div style="text-align: right;">\$ 33,463</div>			
TRAINEE TRAVEL <i>(Describe)</i>			
R. Ssekubugu return air travel, ground visa fees <input type="text" value="Personal Info"/> TBN new admit air travel, ground travel and visa fees - \$3,311; Sandwich PhD travel to JHU including air and ground travel, visa fees, housing and per diem - \$20,442; trainee travel to a conference including air travel, per diem and hotel - \$3,500. <div style="text-align: right;">\$ 30,314</div>			
TRAINING-RELATED EXPENSES <i>(including Health Insurance when applicable – see new Instructions)</i>			
In-country workshops, regional non-degree training and conference registration - \$11,555; training materials (books, computers, etc.) - \$14,203; health insurance - \$4,511 <div style="text-align: right;">\$ 30,269</div>			
TOTAL DIRECT COSTS FOR NEXT BUDGET PERIOD <i>(Also enter on Page 1, Item 8a)</i>			\$ 165,205

BUDGET JUSTIFICATION

GRANT NUMBER
5D43TW001508

Provide a detailed budget justification for those line items and amounts that represent a significant change from that previously recommended. Use continuation pages if necessary.

All budgeted line items are as previously recommended, however, we are cost sharing tuition cost for new degree admit (TBN) for the 2010/2011 academic year to the Johns Hopkins Bloomberg School of Public Health with the JHU AITRP program. This is due to our grant's tuition cap. We are requesting a stipend of \$26,000 for the new degree student at JHU in order to provide equity with JHU AITRP program which sets it's stipend at that level. The advanced research training of \$15,000 budgeted for in the original submission has been re-budgeted to allow for continuation of Robert Ssekubugu's 2nd year studies. His 2nd year tuition will also be covered by JHU AITRP program. In addition, we have requested funding for a conference so a selected trainee whose abstract is accepted can attend an international scientific conference and present his/her funding.

CURRENT BUDGET PERIOD

FROM
04/01/2009

THROUGH
03/31/2010

Explain any estimated unobligated balance (including prior year carryover) that is greater than 25% of the current year's total budget. We do not anticipate to have a carryover greater than 25% of current year's total budget. The remaining funds from current budget period will cover costs for term 4 for John Baptist Bwanika which include tuition, stipend and course materials plus travel expenses for sandwich PhD trainee Fred Nalugoda between April and June 2010.

Program Director/Principal Investigator (Last, First, Middle): Gray, Ronald H.

PROGRESS REPORT SUMMARY	GRANT NUMBER 5D43TW001508	
	PERIOD COVERED BY THIS REPORT	
PROGRAM DIRECTOR / PRINCIPAL INVESTIGATOR Ronald H. Gray	FROM 04/01/2009	THROUGH 03/31/10
APPLICANT ORGANIZATION Johns Hopkins University		
TITLE OF PROJECT (Repeat title shown in Item 1 on first page) International Training/Research in Population and Health, Uganda		
A. Human Subjects (Complete Item 6 on the Face Page)		
Involvement of Human Subjects	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No Change Since Previous Submission	<input type="checkbox"/> Change
B. Vertebrate Animals (Complete Item 7 on the Face Page)		
Use of Vertebrate Animals	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No Change Since Previous Submission	<input type="checkbox"/> Change
C. Select Agent Research	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No Change Since Previous Submission	<input type="checkbox"/> Change
D. Multiple PD/PI Leadership Plan	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No Change Since Previous Submission	<input type="checkbox"/> Change
E. Human Embryonic Stem Cell Line(s) Used	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No Change Since Previous Submission	<input type="checkbox"/> Change

SEE PHS 2590 INSTRUCTIONS.

WOMEN AND MINORITY INCLUSION; See PHS 398 Instructions. Use Inclusion Enrollment Report Format Page and, if necessary, Targeted/Planned Enrollment Format Page.

A. Aims of the program have not changed. The objectives are to train Ugandan scientists in disciplines of relevance to research and program management on population and health via degree training at Makerere and other regional universities, and at Johns Hopkins University, and diploma or short-course training in the region or the U.S. We continue to cost-share trainee expenses with other programs where possible in order to leverage available funding. Because of cost-sharing in this project period number of trainees were able to start or continue long-term, degree training. We are also able to cost-share travel expenses by combining training and research work on other NIH grants.

B. See attached pages

C. US-based long term trainees:

In the fourth reporting period from April, 2009 to March, 2009 two long term trainees have completed their degree training at JHU, one is continuing and one begun training in the fall of 2009.

Adrian Musiige – Dr. Adrian Musiige completed his MPH training in May 2009 and returned to Uganda where he serves as a Medical Officer for the Rakai Health Sciences Program (RSHP). In this capacity he now directs the Rakai Community Cohort Study (RCCS) His final capstone project was titled: "Trends in HIV disease severity at enrollment into HIV care in Rakai, Uganda," which showed a failure of men to access care until late stage disease which adversely affected prognosis. He has presented his findings at international meetings and

Victor Ssempijja – Mr. Ssempijja completed his ScM in Biostatistics in May 2009. He has returned to Uganda and currently serves as a data management supervisor for the Rakai Health Sciences Program. His final dissertation research project was titled: "Bayesian Methods of Monitoring Clinical Trials. An application to Rakai Circumcision Clinical Randomised Trial." Since the start of his training to date, he has been a co-author on nine peer-reviewed publications which are listed at the end of this report. His most recent abstract:

"Bayesian Monitoring of the Randomized Trial of Male Circumcision for HIV Prevention in Rakai, Uganda: Statistical Alternatives and Public Health Implications" was accepted to the 2010 Conference on Retroviruses and Opportunistic Infections in San Francisco which will take place February 16-19. His long-term training was co-sponsored by JHU Fogarty AITRP grant, PI: Beyrer and this collaboration will also support his attendance at the conference.

John Baptist Bwanika – Mr. Bwanika begun his training in the fall of 2008 as a special degree student in the department of Biostatistics. [Personal Info]

[Personal Info] he was accepted into the MHS program in Demography where he continues to expand his training in statistical methods. He will be graduating in May 2010 and the title of his final research projects is: "Mortality among HIV-infected adults in Rakai population before and after availability of HAART." Mr. Bwanika has been a co-author on four peer-reviewed publications which are listed at the end of this report. At the October 2009 Fogarty Annual Meeting of PIs in Bethesda, he also presented a poster titled: "Age at first sex in Rakai, Uganda". His degree training is co-sponsored by JHU Fogarty AITRP grant, PI: Beyrer in order to leverage available funding.

Robert Ssekubugu – Mr. Ssekubugu begun his MHS in International Health degree training in August 2009. He is scheduled to return to Uganda in June 2010 in order to begin a field-based research project. Upon completion of the project he is scheduled to return to JHU for the 4th term of the 2010/2011 academic year in order to complete his degree requirements and graduate in May 2011. His degree training is co-sponsored by JHU Fogarty AITRP grant, PI: Beyrer in order to leverage available funding.

Uganda-based long term trainees:

Sandwich PhD Trainees

Mr. Tom Lutalo currently holds the position of the head of the data management and biostatistics unit. He started his sandwich PhD program in May 2009 and he is developing the concept proposal for presentation at Makerere University and the local IRB for review and approval.

Mr. Fred Nalugoda, - completed required courses at JHU in 2008 and continues with the analysis of the demography of marriage and marital dissolution. [Unpublished]

[Unpublished]

Dr. Godfrey Kigozi – [Unpublished]

[Unpublished]

[Unpublished]

He obtained provisional admission to the PhD program and will be presenting full proposal in March 2010.

Dr. Gertrude Nakigozi - [Unpublished]

[Unpublished]

She obtained provisional admission to the PhD program and will be presenting her full proposal in March 2010. She is currently taking two courses at JHSPH which will count towards her PhD training at Makerere.

Masters training

Mr. Robert Kairania, a counselor supervisor, is finishing training for a MA degree in counseling psychology at the Association of Counselors in Nairobi, Kenya. He is scheduled to complete his training in 2010. Mr. Joseph Sekasanvu, data supervisor is continuing his MSC training in clinical epidemiology and biostatistics at Makerere University in Kampala, Uganda. He is also scheduled to graduate in May 2010. Ms. Barbara Ssekasi is partially supported for her MBA focused on management of health care programs at Makerere University and will complete the program in 2010. Ms. Susan Mawemuko was accepted to an MBA program at Bath University in the UK and her support from this grant covers living expenses. She is scheduled to graduate in 2010.

Ms. Nehemiah Koghoma was partially supported for the completion of her MSc training at Uganda Martyrs University, Nkozi and graduated in 2009. She is currently serving as a coordinator of the circumcision activities for the Rakai Health Sciences Program. Mr. Edward Kimera completed MA training in social administration and also graduated in 2009. Mr. Dan Namuguzi completed his MSc training in surgery at Makerere University in 2009. Mrs. Rebecca Kakembo completed her MBA in 2009 which focused on management of health care programs at the Uganda Martyrs University, Nkozi and holds a position of the deputy program administrator at RHSP.

Batchelor training

Mr. Richard Mwanika is continuing BBLT (Bachelor in Biological Laboratory Technology) training at Makerere University and is scheduled to complete his training in May 2010. Mr. Bryan Mpoza begun BBLT training in August 2009 and will continue for the remainder of the funding period. Both are receiving training in general laboratory procedures and management, as well as specific testing. Mr. Eugene Baale, laboratory technician is continuing his 2nd year BSc training in general lab management and testing at the Kyambogo University in Uganda and is scheduled to complete his studies in May 2011. Mr. Mathias Mbaziira begun his first year of the BP&L program in August 2009 which is projected to last three years. Ms. Betty Nanteza is pursuing BBA in administration and management of health care organizations and will graduate in May 2010. Ms. Immaculate Nalubega is continuing BA training in guidance and counseling at Kampala International University and is schedule to complete her studies in May 2011.

Mr. Deus Kiwanuka completed BA training in gender and development in 2009. Mr. Stephen Juuko completed BA training in computer science and is currently a research assistant at the Rakai Health Science Program. Mr. Many Yeku completed the BBLT program last year and is a laboratory technologist with RHSP. Susan Namatovu competed BA in business administration with concentration on health administration.

Diploma Training

Bazaale Jeremiah is on full time, one-year training in health services management at Uganda Martyrs University in Nkozi. The course will be completed in November 2010.

Isanga Umar Idd is undertaking a three-year, full time diploma in pharmacy at Makerere University. He started in July 2009 and will be completed in June 2012. This grant is providing partial support for his training.

Namuli Janice is a logistics assistant and she is undertaking a one-year course in logistics procurement for health care organizations. The course will be completed in June 2010.

Ms. Viola Nkalubo completed the diploma training in community health at AMREF in Nairobi, Kenya in 2009.

Workshops/Conference

Fred Nalugoda (Program Director), Joseph Sembatya (Head, Community Services) and Agnes Nantong (Program Administrator) attended a 3-month administrative law course from October 2009 to January 2010 at Makerere University which prepared them to manage a complex research and health care delivery organization in a Ugandan setting.

In July 2009 Noah Kiwanuka and Joseph Kagaayi attended the IAS international conference on HIV/AIDS in Cape Town South Africa.

In November 14 – 18th, 2009, the following people attended a Family Planning Conference in Kampala organized by the JHU Gates Institute: Godfrey Kigozi, Rajab Kakaire, and Fred Nalugoda.

Since July 2009, three data management officers are attending data management and software administration workshops. The course will be completed in May 2010.

In November 2009, two laboratory technicians attended a three-day workshop for lab technicians in Kabaale, Uganda and two laboratory technicians attended similar one-week training in Nairobi, Kenya in October 2009.

Monicah Rullonga currently the human resource manager attended one week HR training in South Africa in November 2009.

All heads of departments, their deputies and other senior investigators have attended a two-day training in leadership and management in Kampala, Uganda on January 20 and 21st 2010.

Administrative challenges:

Cap on tuition spending continues to pose a major administrative as well as programmatic challenge. Rising tuition costs, especially in the US, and a 20% of direct cost tuition cap remains a major challenge. We continue to collaborate and cost-share with other programs, especially Fogarty AITRP, in order to provide maximum training opportunities.

CareerTrack database requirement provides additional time burden on administrative staff. Due to the size of the program and available funding a Program Coordinator is only able to spend EFFORT of her time on administering the training leaving little availability for time consuming collection of CareerTrack information, especially historical trainees who have left the program many years ago.

Long term program accomplishments:

All trainees have returned to Uganda and there has been no "brain drain". All trainees are actively involved in policy relevant population and health research. Persons trained under this award have made significant contributions to research in Uganda, and contributions to the scientific literature. Most trainees have also become trainers for MPH students from Makerere University who have an annual internship with field and service programs. The trainees have added to the critical mass of Ugandan researchers, fostering in-country collaborations and capacity building.

Future plans

In the final year of the current grant we will continue to provide support for Mr. Bwanika who will graduate from the MHS program in May 2010 and Mr. Ssekubugu who will complete all MHS degree requirements in May 2011. All four sandwich PhD trainees will continue with their research work and graduation is expected for Mr. Nalugoda. In addition, we plan to provide support for a still TBN new degree student at JHSPH, cost-sharing tuition with JHU AITRP program.

Pending Support

PUBLICATIONS:

- Wawer MJ, Makumbi F, Kigozi G, Serwadda D, Watya S, **Nalugoda F**, Buwembo D, **Ssempijja V**, Kiwanuka N, Moulton LH, Sewankambo NK, Reynolds SJ, Quinn TC, Opendi P, Iga B, Ridzon R, Laeyendecker O, Gray RH. Circumcision in HIV-infected men and its effect on HIV transmission to female partners in Rakai, Uganda: a randomised controlled trial. *Lancet*. 2009 Jul 18;374(9685):229-37. MS133329.
- Johnson KE, Sherman ME, **Ssempijja V**, Tobian AA, Zenilman JM, Duggan MA, **Kigozi G**, Serwadda D, Wawer MJ, Quinn TC, Rabkin CS, Gray RH. Foreskin inflammation is associated with HIV and herpes simplex virus type-2 infections in Rakai, Uganda. *AIDS*. 2009 Sep 10;23(14):1807-15. PMC2752438.
- Tobian AA, **Ssempijja V**, **Kigozi G**, Oliver AE, Serwadda D, Makumbi F, Nalugoda FK, Iga B, Reynolds SJ, Wawer MJ, Quinn TC, Gray RH. Incident HIV and herpes simplex virus type 2 infection among men in Rakai, Uganda. *AIDS*. 2009 Jul 31;23(12):1589-94. PMC2715553.
- Kiggundu V**, Watya S, **Kigozi G**, Serwadda D, **Nalugoda F**, Buwembo D, Settuba A, Anyokorit M, Nkale J, **Kighoma N**, **Ssempijja V**, Wawer M, Gray RH. The number of procedures required to achieve optimal competency with male circumcision: findings from a randomized trial in Rakai, Uganda. *BJU Int*. 2009 Aug;104(4):529-32. Epub 2009 Apr 21. PMC2748867.
- Tobian AA, Serwadda D, Quinn TC, **Kigozi G**, Gravitt PE, Laeyendecker O, Charvat B, **Ssempijja V**, Riedesel M, Oliver AE, Nowak RG, Moulton LH, Chen MZ, Reynolds SJ, Wawer MJ, Gray RH. Male circumcision for the prevention of HSV-2 and HPV infections and syphilis. *N Engl J Med*. 2009 Mar 26;360(13):1298-309. PMID: PMC2676895.
- Tobian AA, Charvat B, **Ssempijja V**, **Kigozi G**, Serwadda D, Makumbi F, Iga B, Laeyendecker O, Riedesel M, Oliver A, Chen MZ, Reynolds SJ, Wawer MJ, Gray RH, Quinn TC. Factors associated with the prevalence and incidence of herpes simplex virus type 2 infection among men in Rakai, Uganda. *J Infect Dis*. 2009 Apr 1;199(7):945-9. PMID: PMC2789195.
- Tobian AA, **Ssempijja V**, **Kigozi G**, Oliver AE, Serwadda D, Makumbi F, **Nalugoda FK**, Iga B, Reynolds SJ, Wawer MJ, Quinn TC, Gray RH. Incident HIV and herpes simplex virus type 2 infection among men in Rakai, Uganda. *AIDS*. 2009 Jul 31;23(12):1589-94. PMID: PMC2715553.
- Laeyendecker O, Redd AD, **Lutalo T**, Gray RH, Wawer M, **Ssempijja V**, Gamiel J, **Bwanika JB**, Makumbi F, **Nalugoda F**, Opendi P, **Kigozi G**, Ndyababo A, Iga B, Kiwanuka N, Sewankambo N, Reynolds SJ, Serwadda D, Quinn TC. Frequency of long-term nonprogressors in HIV-1 seroconverters From Rakai Uganda. *J Acquir Immune Defic Syndr*. 2009 Nov 1;52(3):316-9. (PMC pending)
- Slymaker E, **Bwanika JB**, Kasamba I, **Lutalo T**, Maher D, Todd J. Trends in age at first sex in Uganda: evidence from Demographic and Health Survey data and longitudinal cohorts in Masaka and Rakai. *Sex Transm Infect*. 2009 Apr;85 Suppl 1:i12-9. PMID: PMC2654114.
- Mills LA, Kagaayi J, **Nakigozi G**, Galiwango RM, Ouma J, Shott JP, **Ssempijja V**, Gray RH, Wawer MJ, Serwadda D, Quinn TC, Reynolds SJ. Utility of a point-of-care malaria rapid diagnostic test for excluding malaria as the cause of fever among HIV-positive adults in rural Rakai, Uganda. *Am J Trop Med Hyg*. 2010 Jan;82(1):145-7. (PMC pending)
- Mills LA, Kagaayi J, Shott JP, Newell K, **Bwanika JB**, **Ssempijja V**, Aluma S, Quinn TC, Reynolds SJ, Gray RH. Performance of a prototype malaria rapid diagnostic test versus thick film microscopy among HIV-positive subjects in rural Rakai, Uganda. *Trans R Soc Trop Med Hyg*. 2009 Sep 16. (PMC pending)
- Todd J, Cremin I, McGrath N, **Bwanika JB**, Wringe A, Marston M, Kasamba I, Mushati P, **Lutalo T**, Hosegood V, Zaba B. Reported number of sexual partners: comparison of data from four African longitudinal studies. *Sex Transm Infect*. 2009 Apr;85 Suppl 1:i72-80. PMID: PMC2654146.
- Reynolds SJ, **Nakigozi G**, Newell K, Ndyababo A, Galiwango R, Boaz I, Quinn TC, Gray R, Wawer M, Serwadda D. Failure of immunologic criteria to appropriately identify antiretroviral treatment failure in Uganda. *AIDS*. 2009 Mar 27;23(6):697-700. PMID: PMC2720562.

Program Director/Principal Investigator (Last, First, Middle): Gray, Ronald H.

Kigozi G, Wawer M, Ssettuba A, Kagaayi J, **Nalugoda F**, Watya S, Mangen FW, Kiwanuka N, Bacon MC, **Lutalo T**, Serwadda D, Gray RH. Foreskin surface area and HIV acquisition in Rakai, Uganda (size matters). *AIDS*. 2009 Oct 23;23(16):2209-13. (PMC pending)

Redd AD, Dabitao D, Bream JH, Charvat B, Laeyendecker O, Kiwanuka N, **Lutalo T**, **Kigozi G**, Tobian AA, Gamiel J, Neal JD, Oliver AE, Margolick JB, Sewankambo N, Reynolds SJ, Wawer MJ, Serwadda D, Gray RH, Quinn TC. Microbial translocation, the innate cytokine response, and HIV-1 disease progression in Africa. *Proc Natl Acad Sci U S A*. 2009 Apr 21;106(16):6718-23. Epub 2009 Apr 8. PMID: PMC2667149.

Table 15
Annual Update of NIH/FIC Grant-supported Trainees' Projects
April 1, 2009-March 31, 2010

Trainee Research Project Title	Trainee Name	Title/number of grant supporting research project	Name of Mentor	Are human subjects involved in the research project? If yes, list the U.S. and foreign institutions where IRB approval has been obtained.
Trends in HIV disease severity at enrollment into HIV care in Rakai, Uganda	Adrian Musiige	D43TW001508	Ronald Gray	Secondary data analysis only; Western Institutional Review Board (WIRB) Prot# 20050780 and Uganda Virus Research Institute Science and Ethics Committee (UVRI SEC) FWA# FWA00001354; IRB00001693
Mortality among HIV-infected adults in Rakai population before and after availability of HAART	John Baptist Bwanika	D43TW001508	Ronald Gray	Secondary data analysis only; WIRB Prot# 20050780 and 20031318; UVRI SEC FWA# FWA00001354; IRB00001693
Bayesian Methods of Monitoring Clinical Trials. An application to Rakai Circumcision Clinical Randomised Trial	Victor Ssempijja	D43TW001508	Ronald Gray	Secondary data analysis only; WIRB Prot# 20030586; UVRI SEC FWA# FWA00001354; IRB00001693
Entry into Marriage and Health Effects	Fred Nalugoda	D43TW001508	Ronald Gray/David Serwadda	Secondary data analysis only; WIRB Prot# 20050780 and 20031318; Makerere University School of Public Health IRB FWA00011353; IRB00005876
Non-enrolment and non-adherence to care among HIV-Positive Patients in Rakai district	Gertrude Nakigozi	D43TW001508	Ronald Gray/David Serwadda	Secondary data analysis only; Western Institutional Review Board (WIRB) Prot# 20050780 and Makerere University School of Public Health IRB FWA00011353; IRB00005876; PENDING
Safety of medical male circumcision, virological response and wound healing among positive men	Godfrey Kigozi	D43TW001508	Ronald Gray/David Serwadda	Secondary data analysis only; Western Institutional Review Board (WIRB) Prot# 20030586 and Makerere University School of Public Health IRB FWA00011353; IRB00005876; PENDING

GRANT NUMBER	INSTITUTION	PROGRAM DIRECTOR
5D43TW001508	Johns Hopkins University	Ronald H. Gray

Table 10
In-Country Collaborating Institutions and Individuals

Country	In-Country Key Contact & phone, fax, email	In-Country Institution and address
Uganda	David Serwadda Tel: 031-2263.158/9 041-4543.872 041-4545.001 Fax: 041-4533.957 <u>dserwada@infocom.co.ug</u>	Makerere University School of Public Health Room 219 Old Mulago Hill Road New Mulago Hospital Complex P.O Box 7051, Kampala Uganda

Trainee Diversity Report

This report format should NOT be used for data collection from trainees.

Training Grant Title: International Training/Research in Population and Health, Uganda

Total Number of Appointed: 30

Grant Number: 5D43TW001508

PART A. TOTAL TRAINEE APPOINTMENTS REPORT: Number of Trainees Appointed by Ethnicity and Race				
Ethnic Category	Females	Males	Sex/Gender Unknown or Not Reported	Total
Hispanic or Latino				**
Not Hispanic or Latino	10	20		30
Unknown (individuals not reporting ethnicity)				
Ethnic Category: Total of All Trainees*				*
Racial Categories				
American Indian/Alaska Native				
Asian				
Native Hawaiian or Other Pacific Islander				
Black or African American	10	20		30
White				
More Than One Race				
Unknown or Not Reported				
Racial Categories: Total of All Trainees*				*
PART B. HISPANIC TRAINEE APPOINTMENTS REPORT: Number of Hispanics or Latinos Appointed				
Racial Categories	Females	Males	Sex/Gender Unknown or Not Reported	Total
American Indian or Alaska Native				
Asian				
Native Hawaiian or Other Pacific Islander				
Black or African American				
White				
More Than One Race				
Unknown or Not Reported				
Racial Categories: Total of Hispanics or Latinos**				**
PART C. TRAINEES WITH DISABILITIES OR FROM DISADVANTAGED BACKGROUNDS				
Number of Trainees with Disabilities:				0
Number of Trainees from Disadvantaged Backgrounds:				0

(*) (**) These totals must agree.

Inclusion Enrollment Report

This report format should NOT be used for data collection from study participants.

Study Title: Community Effects of MC on HIV Epidemic with Nested Clinical Research
 Total Enrollment: 18,279 Protocol Number: 20082135
 Grant Number: 22006.03

PART A. TOTAL ENROLLMENT REPORT: Number of Subjects Enrolled to Date (Cumulative) by Ethnicity and Race				
Ethnic Category	Females	Males	Sex/Gender Unknown or Not Reported	Total
Hispanic or Latino				**
Not Hispanic or Latino	8,221	10,058		18,279
Unknown (individuals not reporting ethnicity)				
Ethnic Category: Total of All Subjects*	8,221	10,058		18,279 *
Racial Categories				
American Indian/Alaska Native				
Asian				
Native Hawaiian or Other Pacific Islander				
Black or African American	8,221	10,058		18,279
White				
More Than One Race				
Unknown or Not Reported				
Racial Categories: Total of All Subjects*	8,221	10,058		18,279 *
PART B. HISPANIC ENROLLMENT REPORT: Number of Hispanics or Latinos Enrolled to Date (Cumulative)				
Racial Categories	Females	Males	Sex/Gender Unknown or Not Reported	Total
American Indian or Alaska Native				
Asian				
Native Hawaiian or Other Pacific Islander				
Black or African American				
White				
More Than One Race				
Unknown or Not Reported				
Racial Categories: Total of Hispanics or Latinos**				**

* These totals must agree.
 ** These totals must agree.

Inclusion Enrollment Report

This report format should NOT be used for data collection from study participants.

Study Title: Randomized Trial of Male Circ. STD, HIV & Behav. Effects in Men, Women & Community, Uganda
 Total Enrollment: 5893 Protocol Number: 20021786
 Grant Number: 22006.02

PART A. TOTAL ENROLLMENT REPORT: Number of Subjects Enrolled to Date (Cumulative) by Ethnicity and Race				
Ethnic Category	Females	Males	Sex/Gender Unknown or Not Reported	Total
Hispanic or Latino				**
Not Hispanic or Latino	3,539	2,354		5,893
Unknown (individuals not reporting ethnicity)				
Ethnic Category: Total of All Subjects*	3,539	2,354		5,893 *
Racial Categories				
American Indian/Alaska Native				
Asian				
Native Hawaiian or Other Pacific Islander				
Black or African American	3,539	2,354		5,893
White				
More Than One Race				
Unknown or Not Reported				
Racial Categories: Total of All Subjects*	3,539	2,354		5,893 *
PART B. HISPANIC ENROLLMENT REPORT: Number of Hispanics or Latinos Enrolled to Date (Cumulative)				
Racial Categories	Females	Males	Sex/Gender Unknown or Not Reported	Total
American Indian or Alaska Native				
Asian				
Native Hawaiian or Other Pacific Islander				
Black or African American				
White				
More Than One Race				
Unknown or Not Reported				
Racial Categories: Total of Hispanics or Latinos**				**

* These totals must agree.
 ** These totals must agree.

Inclusion Enrollment Report

This report format should NOT be used for data collection from study participants.

Study Title: Rakai Community Cohort Study
 Total Enrollment: 52,008 Protocol Number: 20031318
 Grant Number: N/A

PART A. TOTAL ENROLLMENT REPORT: Number of Subjects Enrolled to Date (Cumulative) by Ethnicity and Race				
Ethnic Category	Females	Males	Sex/Gender Unknown or Not Reported	Total
Hispanic or Latino				**
Not Hispanic or Latino	28,344	23,664		52,008
Unknown (individuals not reporting ethnicity)				
Ethnic Category: Total of All Subjects*	28,344	23,664		52,008 *
Racial Categories				
American Indian/Alaska Native				
Asian				
Native Hawaiian or Other Pacific Islander				
Black or African American	28,344	23,664		52,008
White				
More Than One Race				
Unknown or Not Reported				
Racial Categories: Total of All Subjects*	28,344	23,664		52,008 *
PART B. HISPANIC ENROLLMENT REPORT: Number of Hispanics or Latinos Enrolled to Date (Cumulative)				
Racial Categories	Females	Males	Sex/Gender Unknown or Not Reported	Total
American Indian or Alaska Native				
Asian				
Native Hawaiian or Other Pacific Islander				
Black or African American				
White				
More Than One Race				
Unknown or Not Reported				
Racial Categories: Total of Hispanics or Latinos**				**

* These totals must agree.
 ** These totals must agree.

For New and Renewal Applications (PHS 398) – DO NOT SUBMIT UNLESS REQUESTED
For Non-competing Progress Reports (PHS 2590) – Submit only Active Support for Key Personnel

PHS 398/2590 OTHER SUPPORT

GRAY, RONALD H.

ACTIVE

U01-AI075115-01A1 (Gray, Ronald H.) 09/01/2007-08/31/2012
NIH/NIAID \$1,238,811
Circumcision: HIV/STIs and behavioral effects in a RCT and Post RCT Surveillance, Rakai, Uganda

Major goal of this project is to assess circumcision effectiveness and sexual risk behaviors in participants of the circumcision clinical trial and to assess the efficacy for HSV-2 and HPV prevention using samples collected during the trial of "Male Circumcision for HIV Prevention." Role: PI

3U01-AI075115-03S1 (Gray, Ronald H.) 09/22/2009-08/31/2011
NIH/NIAID \$1,238,811
Circumcision: HIV/STIs and behavioral effects in a RCT and Post RCT Surveillance, Rakai, Uganda
HPV Supplement

Major goal of this project is to assess the efficacy of male circumcision for HR-HPV prevention in HIV-negative and positive men and to determine prevalence, incidence and clearance of HPV, to assess the efficacy of circumcision for reduction of genital HR-HPV infection in female partners of HIV-infected and uninfected male trial participants.

R01 HD 050180 (Wawer, Maria J.) 07/15/2005 – 05/30/2010
NICHD \$1,407,113
ARV Effects on HIV-Epidemiology and Behaviors, Rakai, Uganda

Major goals of this project are to assess community level HIV prevalence, incidence, emergence and transmission of drug resistant quasiespecies, identify novel drug-resistant mutations, monitor sexual and other risk behaviors among HIV+ and HIV- community members, determine the effects of ARVs on HIV-related stigma and the effects of stigma on VCT and ARV acceptance in Rakai, Uganda. Role: Co-Inv

D43TW01508 (Gray, Ronald H.) 09/30/2006 – 09/29/2011
Fogarty International Center \$165,203
International Training/Research in Population and Health

Major goal is to train Ugandan scientists in disciplines relevant to population and reproductive health, including epidemiology, demography, behavioral and social sciences, clinical and basic sciences. Role: PI

N/A (Tsui, Amy) 7/01/2008-4/01/2015
Private Source \$4,078,202

Private Source Role: Co-Inv.

1R01 AI071906 (Gray) Subcontract 05/01/2008 – 04/30/2011
The University of Alabama at Birmingham \$38,540
Host Genetic Epidemiology in HIV-1Discordant African Couples and Other Cohorts.

Major goal is to address the Office of AIDS Research 2007 goal of identifying genetic factors that explain highly variable responses to the infection and its sequelae. Role: PI

Program Director/Principal Investigator: Gray, Ronald H.

Private Source

(Last, first, middle)

(Wawer, Maria J.)

11/01/2008-11/01/2013

EFFORT

Private Source

\$2,854,310

Community Effects of Male Circumcision (MC) on HIV Epidemic, with nested MC-related Clinical and Basic Science Research

Major goal of the study is to address whether MC services result in a net reduction of HIV incidence in the general population of 50 rural Rakai villages. This multidisciplinary program will provide crucial information on the effectiveness of MC for HIV prevention, help define guidelines for MC provision in both HIV-uninfected and infected men, and will generate new knowledge and insights for the future development of microbicides and mucosal HIV vaccines. Role: Co-Inv

1 R01 HD060460-01A1 (Brahmbhatt, Heena) 04/01/2009-03/31/2012
HIV/HAART and Pregnancy/Contraception in Rakai, \$175,000
Uganda

EFFORT

Major goal of the study is to assess: (i) determinants of contraceptive use and impact of fertility desires and intention on contraceptive use and pregnancy rates, (ii) impact of hormonal contraceptives on HIV disease progression as well as the impact of ARTs on fertility outcomes, contraceptive use and high risk behaviors, and (iii) fertility outcomes and contraceptive use among HIV-concordant and serodiscordant couples. Role: Co-Inv

R01 HD061092 (Gray) Subcontract 04/01/2009-03/31/2014
Columbia University \$54,157
Rakai Adolescent Project (RAP)

EFFORT

Major goal of the study is to examine the changing behavioral, biological, and contextual risk of HIV infection among adolescents and young adults within the Rakai Community Cohort Study (RCCS). Role: PI

Remaining support comes from departmental discretionary fund and endowed professorship.

PENDING

Pending Support

Pending Support

OVERLAP

If pending applications are awarded, effort will be adjusted accordingly.

For New and Renewal Applications (PHS 398) – DO NOT SUBMIT UNLESS REQUESTED
For Non-competing Progress Reports (PHS 2590) – Submit only Active Support for Key Personnel

PHS 398/2590 OTHER SUPPORT

WAWER, MARIA J.

ACTIVE

U01-AI075115-01A1	(Gray, Ronald H.)	09/01/2007-08/31/2012	EFFORT
NIH/NIAID		\$1,238,811	

Circumcision: HIV/STIs and behavioral effects in a RCT and Post RCT Surveillance, Rakai, Uganda

Major goal of this project is to assess circumcision effectiveness and sexual risk behaviors in participants of the circumcision clinical trial and to assess the efficacy for HSV-2 and HPV prevention using samples collected during the trial of "Male Circumcision for HIV Prevention." Role: Co-PI

R01 HD 050180	(Wawer, Maria J.)	07/15/2005 – 05/30/2010	EFFORT
NICHD		\$1,407,113	

ARV Effects on HIV-Epidemiology and Behaviors, Rakai, Uganda

Major goals of this project are to assess community level HIV prevalence, incidence, emergence and transmission of drug resistant quasispecies, identify novel drug-resistant mutations, monitor sexual and other risk behaviors among HIV+ and HIV- community members, determine the effects of ARVs on HIV-related stigma and the effects of stigma on VCT and ARV acceptance in Rakai, Uganda. Role: PI

Private Source	(Wawer, Maria J.)	11/01/2008-11/01/2013	EFFORT
Private Source		\$2,854,310	

Community Effects of Male Circumcision (MC) on HIV Epidemic, with nested MC-related Clinical and Basic Science Research

Major goal of the study is to address whether MC services result in a net reduction of HIV incidence in the general population of 50 rural Rakai villages. This multidisciplinary program will provide crucial information on the effectiveness of MC for HIV prevention, help define guidelines for MC provision in both HIV-uninfected and infected men, and will generate new knowledge and insights for the future development of microbicides and mucosal HIV vaccines. Role: PI

R01 HD061092 (Gray) Subcontract		04/01/2009-03/31/2014	EFFORT
Columbia University		\$54,157	

Rakai Adolescent Project (RAP)

Major goal of the study is to examine the changing behavioral, biological, and contextual risk of HIV infection among adolescents and young adults within the Rakai Community Cohort Study (RCCS). Role: Co-Inv

Remaining support comes from departmental discretionary fund.

PENDING

Pending Support

Program Director/Principal Investigator: Gray, Ronald H.
(Last, first, middle)

Pending Support

OVERLAP

If pending applications are awarded, effort will be adjusted accordingly.

For New and Renewal Applications (PHS 398) – DO NOT SUBMIT UNLESS REQUESTED
For Non-competing Progress Reports (PHS 2590) – Submit only Active Support for Key Personnel

PHS 398/2590 OTHER SUPPORT

SERWADDA, DAVID

ACTIVE

USGPS000971 CDC	(Serwadda, David)	10/01/07-09/30/12 \$5,500,000	EFFORT
Developing National Capacity for the Management of HIV/AIDS Programs and Support for the Delivery of HIV Prevention, Care and Treatment in Rakai District of the Republic of Uganda Under the President's Emergency Plan for AIDS Relief			
To build health institutional capacity and expand health facilities in Uganda as well as community based provision of comprehensive, sustainable and quality HIV/AIDS services. Role: PI			
	(Serwadda, David)	09/01/06-08/31/11 \$3,600,000	EFFORT
CDC Strengthening applied epidemiology training program in Africa. Role: PI			

Additional salary support comes from Makerere University, School of Public Health.

Dr. Serwadda received consulting compensation from the following grants:

ACTIVE

U01-AI075115-01A1 JHU Subcontract funded by NIH/NIAID	(Gray, Ronald)	09/01/2007-08/31/2012 \$1,238,811	EFFORT (no salary)
Circumcision: HIV/STIs and behavioral effects in a RCT and Post RCT Surveillance, Rakai, Uganda Major goal of this project is to assess circumcision effectiveness and sexual risk behaviors in participants of the circumcision clinical trial and to assess the efficacy for HSV-2 and HPV prevention using samples collected during the trial of "Male Circumcision for HIV Prevention." Role: Sub PI			
R01 HD 050180 JHU Subcontract funded by NICHD	(Wawer, Maria J)	07/15/2005 – 05/30/2010 \$1,407,113	EFFORT (no salary)
ARV Effects on HIV-Epidemiology and Behaviors, Rakai, Uganda Major goals of this project are to assess community level HIV prevalence, incidence, emergence and transmission of drug resistant quasiespecies, identify novel drug-resistant mutations, monitor sexual and other risk behaviors among HIV+ and HIV- community members, determine the effects of ARVs on HIV-related stigma and the effects of stigma on VCT and ARV acceptance in Rakai, Uganda. Role: Sub PI			
Private Source Private Source	(Wawer, Maria J.)	09/01/2002 – 02/28/2009 \$1,492,795	EFFORT (no salary)
Male Circumcision Trial for Prevention on HIV and STD Infection in Men, Women and the Community, Rakai, Uganda Major goals of this project are to assess effects of male circumcision on STD rates in males, on HIV+ and STD rates in women. Role: Sub PI			

Program Director/Principal Investigator: Gray, Ronald H.
(Last, first, middle)

Private Source

(Wawer, Maria J.)

11/01/2008-11/01/2013

EFFORT

JHU Subcontracts funded by

\$2,854,310

(no salary)

Private Source

Community Effects of Male Circumcision (MC) on HIV Epidemic, with nested MC-related Clinical and Basic Science Research. Role: Sub PI

Major goal of the study is to address whether MC services result in a net reduction of HIV incidence in the general population of 50 rural Rakai villages. This multidisciplinary program will provide crucial information on the effectiveness of MC for HIV prevention, help define guidelines for MC provision in both HIV-uninfected and infected men, and will generate new knowledge and insights for the future development of microbicides and mucosal HIV vaccines. Role: Sub PI

R01 HD061092 (Gray) Subcontract
Columbia University
Rakai Adolescent Project (RAP)

04/01/2009-03/31/2014
\$54,157

EFFORT

Major goal of the study is to examine the changing behavioral, biological, and contextual risk of HIV infection among adolescents and young adults within the Rakai Community Cohort Study (RCCS).

1 R01 HD060460-01A1 (Brahmbhatt, Heena)
HIV/HAART and Pregnancy/Contraception in Rakai,
Uganda

04/01/2009-03/31/2012
\$175,000

EFFORT

Major goal of the study is to assess: (i) determinants of contraceptive use and impact of fertility desires and intention on contraceptive use and pregnancy rates, (ii) impact of hormonal contraceptives on HIV disease progression as well as the impact of ARTs on fertility outcomes, contraceptive use and high risk behaviors, and (iii) fertility outcomes and contraceptive use among HIV-concordant and serodiscordant couples. Role: Co-Inv

OVERLAP

No overlap.

Program Director/Principal Investigator (Last, first, middle): Gray, Ronald H.

GRANT NUMBER
5D43TW001508

CHECKLIST

1. PROGRAM INCOME (See instructions.)

All applications must indicate whether program income is anticipated during the period(s) for which grant support is requested. If program income is anticipated, use the format below to reflect the amount and source(s).

Budget Period	Anticipated Amount	Source(s)

2. ASSURANCES/CERTIFICATIONS (See instructions.)

In signing the application Face Page, the authorized organizational representative agrees to comply with the policies, assurances and/or certifications listed in the application instructions when applicable. Descriptions of individual assurances/certifications are provided in Part III of the PHS 398, and listed in Part I, 4.1 under Item 14. If unable to certify compliance, where applicable, provide an explanation and place it after the Progress Report (Form Page 5).

3. FACILITIES AND ADMINISTRATIVE (F&A) COSTS

Indicate the applicant organization's most recent F&A cost rate established with the appropriate DHHS Regional Office, or, in the case of for-profit organizations, the rate established with the appropriate PHS Agency Cost Advisory Office.

F&A costs will **not** be paid on construction grants, grants to Federal organizations, grants to individuals, and conference grants. Follow any additional instructions provided for Research Career Awards, Institutional National Research Service Awards, Small Business Innovation Research/Small Business Technology Transfer Grants, foreign grants, and specialized grant applications.

DHHS Agreement dated: 06/10/2008 No Facilities and Administrative Costs Requested.

No DHHS Agreement, but rate established with _____ Date _____

CALCULATION*

Entire proposed budget period: Amount of base \$ 131,742 x Rate applied 8% % = F&A costs \$ 10,539

Add to total direct costs from Form Page 2 and enter new total on Face Page, Item 8b.

*Check appropriate box(es):

Salary and wages base Modified total direct cost base Other base (Explain)

Off-site, other special rate, or more than one rate involved (Explain)

Explanation (Attach separate sheet, if necessary):

Tuition and fees excluded from base

ALL PERSONNEL REPORT

GRANT NUMBER
5D43TW001508

Place this form at the end of the signed original copy of the application. Do not duplicate.

Always list the PD/PI(s). In addition, list all other personnel who participated in the project during the current budget period for at least one person month or more, regardless of the source of compensation (a person month equals approximately 160 hours or 8.3% of annualized effort). Use Cal (calendar), Acad, or Summer to enter months devoted to project.

Commons ID	Name	Degree(s)	SSN (last 4 digits)	Role on Project (e.g. PD/PI, Res. Assoc.)	DoB (MM /YY)	Cal	Acad	Summer
eRA Commons User Name	Gray, Ronald	MD, MSC	Personal Info	PI	Personal Info	EFFORT		
	Wawer, Maria	MD, MHSc		Mentor				
	Serwadda, David	MD, MPH	N/A	Mentor				